

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D5.1: Description of the preliminary flexibility multi-carrier flexibility services for buildings

WP5 – Provision of Flexibility Trade-off Services and Frameworks

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PUBLIC

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Contributors:

Document Section	Author(s)	Reviewer(s)
All	Marcin Adamski (PSNC) Tomasz Ciesielczyk (PSNC)	Matthias Strobbe (IMEC)
T5.1 - Implementation of standardized flexibility frameworks and interfaces	Marcin Adamski (PSNC) Tomasz Ciesielczyk (PSNC) Franciszek Sidorski (PSNC) Youssef Dahman (INETUM) Eduardo Vendrell del Río (INETUM) Gerard Laguna (CIMNE)	
T5.2 - Standardization of proprietary flexibility frameworks and interfaces and comparative analysis	Niklas Friedel (ENK) Michael Niederkofler (ENK)	
T5.3 - BlueBird Flexibility Trading module	Adamski Marcin (PSNC) Ciesielczyk Tomasz (PSNC) Franciszek Sidorski (PSNC)	

Executive Summary

The document contains fundamental information about the software that will be developed within WP5. It is structured into sections corresponding to the individual tasks defined in this work package. For each task, the document provides a concise description of the planned or implemented software components, links to the relevant source code repositories, and illustrative examples of usage scenarios. This structure is intended to give readers a clear overview of the scope, functionality, and practical application of the developed solutions, as well as to facilitate further development, integration, and evaluation activities.

Table of Contents

I. INTRODUCTION	8
II. IMPLEMENTATION OF STANDARDIZED FLEXIBILITY FRAMEWORKS AND INTERFACES (T5.1)	10
II.1. The InterConnect DSO Interface as Foundation	10
II.2. Ontology.....	11
II.2.1. Implemented ontologies in WP5	11
II.2.2. BlueBird for Energy Markets ontology	11
II.2.3. Interconnect DSO standard interface integration.....	12
II.3. Interconnect DSO standard interface - Knowledge engine.....	13
II.4. Software output of T5.1	14
II.4.1. Knowledge Engine (docker)	14
II.4.2. Knowledge Engine Client (python).....	14
III. STANDARDIZATION OF PROPRIETARY FLEXIBILITY FRAMEWORKS AND INTERFACES AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS (T5.2).....	16
III.1. Description of the InterFlex framework	16
III.1.1. InterFlex framework for aggregators	16
III.2. Software Output of T5.2 – Integration of a Technical Flexibility Service Provider with the APG Flexibility Platform	17
III.2.1. System architecture of the APG integration.....	18
III.2.2. Operational workflow of the flexibility service	19
III.2.3. Comparative analysis of flexibility frameworks.....	19
III.3. Pseudocode of the APG interface implementation.....	20
IV. TRADING MANAGER DESCRIPTION (T5.3)	21
IV.1. Market connectors.....	22
IV.1.1. Client for ENTSO-E Transparency market platform.....	22
IV.1.2. Client for accessing BlueBird price forecasting service	23
V. CONCLUSION	24
V.1. Summary of WP5 preliminary technical outputs	24
V.2. Next steps toward D5.2	24
REFERENCES.....	25

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Graph patterns between BlueBird components..... 13

Figure 2. TOU-price definition..... 13

Figure 3. KE docker start command 14

Figure 4. KE client installation command..... 14

Figure 5. KE client initialization command 15

Figure 6. KI handlers for sample measurement client commands 15

Figure 7. KE client registration amd running commnads 15

Figure 8 Generalized conceptual architecture of flexibility aggregation 17

Figure 9. Example pseudocode: OAuth authentication 20

Figure 10. Example pseudocode: Activation handling 20

Figure 11 ENTSO-E Transparency Platform webpage! 22

Figure 12. Sample HTTP request to retrieve data from the Germany day ahead market..... 22

Figure 13. Sample HTTP response to retrieve data from the Germany day ahead market..... 23

List of Tables

Table 1 WP5 repositories..... 9

Table 2. Comparative analysis of flexibility frameworks 20

Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APG	Austrian Transmission System Operator
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CBP	Crowd Balancing Platform
cFSP	Commercial Flexibility Service Provider
D	Deliverable
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
FM	Flexibility Manager
GP	Graph Pattern
KE	Knowledge Engine
KI	Knowledge Interaction
RDF	Resource Description Framework
tFSP	Technical Flexibility Service Provider
TM	Trading Manager
TOU	Time-Of-Use
TSO	Transmission System Operator
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

This document presents and formally records the software development work performed in Work Package 5 (WP5), describing each activity within its corresponding task so that project objectives, technical implementation and resulting software components are clearly linked.

The main objective of this work package is to facilitate communication with electricity markets and grid operators. It aims to establish the essential technical and architectural foundations to enable buildings to function as adaptable energy assets. By promoting seamless data exchange and interoperability, these frameworks are designed to enable buildings to become active participants in energy systems.

The central software component developed within WP5 is the Trading Manager (TM), responsible for acquiring energy price data from multiple electricity markets, including day-ahead, intraday and capacity markets, and delivering this information in a structured, semantically consistent form to other system components. The primary consumer of this data is the Flexibility Manager (FM), a component developed in the broader BlueBird architecture that uses market price signals to optimize the operation of building assets such as HVAC systems, EV charging stations and battery storage. In addition to live market data, the TM also interfaces with a dedicated price forecasting Digital Twin developed within the BlueBird project, enabling forward-looking optimization based on predicted price evolution. To ensure interoperability across heterogeneous market environments and building systems, WP5 further adopts the InterFlex [1] framework (a reference interaction model developed within the EU Horizon 2020 InterFlex project) as a standardized mechanism for representing and exchanging flexibility information between providers, aggregators and market-facing components.

For each task (T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3), the document presents a structured description of the developed software, including its main functionalities, intended role within the overall system architecture, and interactions with other components. In addition, references to the corresponding source code repositories are provided, enabling transparency, reproducibility, and further development. Where appropriate, illustrative examples of software usage are included to demonstrate practical application scenarios and expected behaviour of the implemented solutions.

This deliverable is the first deliverable produced within WP5 and represents an important milestone for the BlueBird project. The software developed and described herein constitutes the initial prototype versions of the WP5 components. These prototypes are intended to validate core concepts, architectural assumptions, and key functionalities rather than to provide fully mature, production-ready solutions.

The implementation work within WP5 will continue throughout the project lifecycle, with ongoing refinement, extension, and optimization of the software components. Future efforts will focus on achieving stable, robust, and fully functional versions that meet all technical, performance, and interoperability requirements of the BlueBird project. Subsequent software releases, including intermediate and final versions, along with their extended functionalities and improvements, will be documented in upcoming WP5 deliverables.

The WP5 software builds directly on the InterConnect [10] DSO standard interface and its Semantic Interoperability Framework, which provide a standardized, open and technology-agnostic communication layer between DSOs, flexibility service providers and building systems through a shared semantic model based on SAREF [2], in particular SAREF4ENER for the energy domain. By using ontologies instead of proprietary data models, the DSO Interface ensures that concepts such as flexibility requests, price signals or capacity constraints are interpreted consistently by all participants.

By grounding WP5 components in this interface and its semantic interoperability approach, BlueBird leverages a mature, reusable foundation already validated in multiple European pilots, so that the preliminary implementations described in D5.1 not only constitute the first prototype of the BlueBird flexibility trading toolchain but also foster the adoption of open standards for flexibility data exchange between DSOs, aggregators and buildings.

Software packages developed within the BlueBird project are available in the main project repository: <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/>. The repository provides access to the source code, documentation, and related resources developed as part of the project. It is intended to support transparency, reproducibility, and further development of the proposed solutions by project partners and external stakeholders.

In particular, the following software packages were developed within Work Package 5:

Table 1 WP5 repositories

Repository	Link
KE python client	https://github.com/BlueBird-project/ke-pyclient
APG-interface	https://github.com/BlueBird-project/APG-Interface-.git
Trading Manager	https://github.com/BlueBird-project/trading-manager
BlueBird market plugins	https://github.com/BlueBird-project/tm-market-plugins

They are described in detail in this document.

II. IMPLEMENTATION OF STANDARDIZED FLEXIBILITY FRAMEWORKS AND INTERFACES (T5.1)

II.1. The InterConnect DSO Interface as Foundation

The implementation work in T5.1 builds upon the DSO Interface standard developed within the [EU Horizon 2020 InterConnect project](#). The DSO Interface was conceived to address a fundamental challenge in the European energy transition: enabling seamless communication between Distribution System Operators (DSOs), flexibility service providers, and building energy management systems across different countries, vendors, and technological platforms.

Traditional integration approaches rely on bilateral agreements in which each pair of systems must define custom data formats, protocol mappings, and API specifications. This creates significant barriers to scalability: every new actor joining the ecosystem requires separate integration projects with each existing participant. The DSO Interface solves this problem through semantic interoperability: instead of exchanging raw data that must be interpreted by application logic, systems exchange semantically annotated information whose meaning is explicitly defined through shared ontologies.

The core innovation lies in the use of the SAREF ontology family, standardized by ETSI. SAREF provides a common vocabulary for energy domain concepts, such as power measurements, flexibility requests, price signals, and temporal constraints, ensuring that all participants share a consistent understanding of exchanged information regardless of their internal implementations. SAREF4ENER, in particular, extends the core SAREF model with energy-specific concepts including flexibility profiles, demand response scenarios, and device capabilities.

The DSO Interface is not merely a data transmission protocol but a complete Semantic Interoperability Framework (SIF) comprising:

- Ontological foundation: SAREF-based semantic models that define energy concepts
- Knowledge Engine: A distributed platform enabling peer-to-peer semantic communication
- Adapter architecture: Generic and Service-Specific Adapters that connect legacy systems to the semantic layer
- Service ecosystem: A registry and marketplace enabling discovery and composition of interoperable services

The practical viability of this framework was extensively validated during InterConnect, a large-scale initiative involving 51 partners across Europe. The DSO Interface and its underlying Knowledge Engine were deployed across seven European pilot sites with over fifty integrators, demonstrating that semantic interoperability through SAREF ontologies enables plug-and-play integration of energy services in real operational environments. This validation at scale provides confidence that the architectural choices adopted by BlueBird's WP5 software components rest on a proven, field-tested foundation rather than a purely theoretical specification. This validation at scale provides confidence that the architectural choices adopted by BlueBird's WP5 software components rest on a proven, field-tested foundation rather than a purely theoretical specification. A detailed white paper on the use and extension of the DSO Interface within the BlueBird project is currently being prepared by INETUM and PSNC and will be published in the near future.

In WP5, BlueBird adopts and extends this foundation to support building-integrated flexibility trading. The ontologies described in Section II.2, the Knowledge Engine deployment detailed in Section II.3, and the software components presented in Section II.4 constitute the practical realization of the DSO Interface within the BlueBird architecture. By grounding WP5 in this mature, standardized framework, BlueBird ensures compatibility with other European energy projects and contributes to the broader adoption of semantic interoperability for grid flexibility services.

The T5.1 task also considered two additional flexibility frameworks referenced in the project proposal: InterFlex [1] and USEF [3] (Universal Smart Energy Framework). The InterFlex framework, developed within the EU Horizon 2020 InterFlex project, defines a generic interaction model for the standardized exchange of flexibility information between providers, aggregators and market- or grid-facing entities; its adoption and integration within WP5 is described in detail in Section III (T5.2). The USEF framework, by contrast, was evaluated during the early stages of T5.1 but was not further pursued in the project. This decision was driven by the broader architectural alignment of BlueBird with the InterConnect DSO Interface and its Semantic Interoperability Framework, which already encompasses the interoperability and market communication objectives that USEF addresses, while offering a more direct continuity with the project's semantic infrastructure and the SAREF ontology ecosystem.

II.2. Ontology

II.2.1. Implemented ontologies in WP5

In order to meet interoperability and versatility expectations, the WP5 framework and interfaces reuse common ontologies like:

- rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
- rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
- xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
- owl: <https://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl>
- time: <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
- SAREF core: <https://saref.etsi.org/core>
- SAREF for Energy Flexibility (SAREF core extension): <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4ener/>
- SAREF for the Smart City domain (SAREF core extension): <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4city>

II.2.2. BlueBird for Energy Markets ontology

For the purposes of the project, the concepts of energy markets and contracts between a market and a customer (represented by TM) have been modelled in the UBFlex for Markets ontology (<https://ubflex.bluebird.eu/market>), which is built on top of the previously mentioned ontologies. This ontology differentiates between market types, such as the day-ahead market and the capacity market

The BlueBird market ontology consists of:

- Market types (ubmarket:MarketType - base class), namely: ubmarket:DayAheadMarket and ubmarket:CapacityMarket
- Market contracts (for capacity market) - ubmarket:FlexContractRequest (market aggregator request for the flexibility offer's availability) and ubmarket:FlexContractOffer (as the response to the request)
- Flexibility baseline - determines the way of designating the baseline: fixed value (s4ener:BaseLine) or dynamic value - determined by the past energy consumption (ubmarket:DynamicBaseline, ubmarket:CalculationMethod)

All these fields and ontologies are integrated into the BIGG Ontology, described in the Deliverable 6.2 “Technical description of the preliminary BlueBird Supportive Platform”, which serves as a unified semantic framework for the project. This ontology is an evolution of the open-source ontology developed in the EU Horizon 2020 BIGG project (Building Information aGGregation, available at <https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/biggonology>), which originally provided a standardized schema for describing buildings, their energy consumption, and associated efficiency measures. For BlueBird, this foundation has been extended to incorporate additional elements required by the project, including energy community links, multi-zone heating and cooling representations, tariff and market information, and capacity market data, while remaining aligned with existing ontologies such as SAREF, CORE, OWL, TIME, BIMERR and FOAF.

This integration combines domain-specific ontologies covering markets, devices, measurements and system modelling with ontologies specifically designed to describe buildings and their associated assets. By consolidating these into a single unified ontology, a consistent and interoperable representation of both physical infrastructure and data flows is provided, allowing for detailed descriptions of building elements alongside operational and contextual data such as measurements, events, and performance indicators.

This unified approach is particularly important for linking market-related information, such as energy prices, demand-response signals, and contractual conditions, with the operation and behaviour of building assets. Through this integration, it becomes possible to connect external signals with internal system responses, for example, by adjusting energy consumption, activating storage systems, or optimising operational strategies based on market conditions.

II.2.3. Interconnect DSO standard interface integration

Data shared within the Knowledge Engine will utilize knowledge interactions (KI), the fundamental communication primitives that define how participants in the network exchange information. A KI specifies both the shape of the data being requested or provided and the interaction pattern used to exchange it. The Knowledge Engine supports four types of KIs organized in two pairs: ASK (proactive query) paired with ANSWER (reactive response), and POST (proactive publication) paired with REACT (reactive subscription). ASK/ANSWER is used when a component needs to retrieve information on demand, while POST/REACT supports event-driven communication where subscribers are notified when new knowledge is published.

The data structure exchanged within each KI is defined by a Graph Pattern (GP), an RDF graph template in which certain elements are replaced by variables. When a KI is executed, these variables are bound to actual values, producing the concrete data being exchanged. GPs provide the semantic backbone of each interaction: they define not only the shape of the data but also its meaning, by referencing shared ontology terms that ensure consistent interpretation across all participants.

Each GP in BlueBird utilizes the SAREF and BlueBird (ubmarket) ontologies to describe energy domain concepts in a standardized way. The GPs used in the KIs between BlueBird actors are presented in the figure below.

Figure 1 Graph patterns between BlueBird components

Graph Patterns for all KI will be published in the BlueBird Git repository. Sample GP configuration for the TOU timeseries data points:

```

tou-price:
  name: "tou-price"
  description: "Data points for TOU (tou_uri) timeseries. "
  prefixes:
    xsd: "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
    saref: "https://saref.etsi.org/core/"
  required_bindings:
    - "tou_uri"
  pattern:
    - '?dp s4ener:belongsToTimeSeries ?tou_uri ; rdf:type s4ener:DataPoint ; saref:hasTimestamp ?ts ;'
    - '  s4ener:hasEffectivePeriod ${ISP_UNIT}; saref:hasResult ?dpr.'
    - '?dpr saref:hasValue ?value ; saref:isMeasuredIn "PLNPerMegawattHour" .'
    
```

Figure 2. TOU-price definition

II.3. Interconnect DSO standard interface - Knowledge engine

The Knowledge Engine (KE, developed by TNO) is an open-source semantic interoperability platform designed to enable intelligent data exchange between different systems (e.g., devices, APIs, databases, services) without relying on a central database. It uses semantic technologies and ontologies to define a shared domain language so that disparate systems can understand, link and reason about data across organizational and technical boundaries. The engine supports distributed networks, keeps data at the source (the KE doesn't store any data, its goal is to provide semantic communication between the clients in the network), and gives participants full control over which data is shared. The data discovery and format are handled by knowledge interactions (Kis), namely:

- **POST** - interaction which publishes *knowledge* to the network.
 - Used to announce facts, events, or updates to the network.
 - Other nodes may subscribe or REACT to this information.

- **REACT** – counter interaction to POST. REACT is triggered when certain knowledge is published. Replies with knowledge conforming to the argument graph pattern and sends knowledge back to the Knowledge Network in the form of the result graph patterns.
- **ASK** - ASK interaction expresses a question or knowledge need. Registered ASK interactions defines the shape of the response from the network (in form of an ANSWER KI)
- **ANSWER** – direct response to an ASK, defines the shape of shared knowledge. If the ANSWER KI's graph pattern matches the ASK, knowledge is shared.

II.4. Software output of T5.1

II.4.1. Knowledge Engine (docker)

KE service sources are available at <https://github.com/TNO/knowledge-engine>. KE service docker is available at the GitHub docker repository. The docker can be started by running the following command:

```
docker run \  
-p 8280:8280 \  
-p 8081:8081 \  
-e KD_URL=https://knowledge-directory.example.org \  
-e KE_RUNTIME_EXPOSED_URL=https://your-domain.example.org:8081 \  
ghcr.io/tno/knowledge-engine/smart-connector:1.4.0
```

Figure 3. KE docker start command

II.4.2. Knowledge Engine Client (python)

KE PYClient (ke-pyclient) is a dedicated Python client library that enables communication with the KE service. It handles the communication process and registers Knowledge Interactions on the KE server. The library provides a convenient mechanism for mapping Knowledge Interaction graph patterns to Python objects and encapsulates the entire communication workflow within a single function call.

The client will be published at <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/ke-pyclient>.

II.4.2.a. Installation

The client can be simply installed via PyPi tool:

```
pip install ke_client==0.16.1
```

Figure 4. KE client installation command

II.4.2.b. Client configuration

Client basic configuration consists of following environmental variables:

- **KE_REST_ENDPOINT** – address of KE's docker rest endpoint
- **KE_KI_CONFIG_PATH** – YAML configuration file containing graph pattern definitions
- **KE_KNOWLEDGE_BASE_ID** – unique client identifier (RDF URI) across the KE network

II.4.2.c. Client initialization

```
# import client:
from ke_client.client import KEClient

# build client instance
ke_client = KEClient.build()
```

Figure 5. KE client initialization command

II.4.2.d. Define KI handlers for sample measurement client

```
# Initialize publish KI handler in the client. 'sensor-data' is the name of the KI's graph pattern
@ke_client.post("sensor-data") 1 usage  tomasz_ciesielczyk *
def post_data():
    sensor_measurements = [{
        "sensor": f'<{ke_client.kb_id}_0>', "temperature": f"{random.randint(a: 10, b: 20)}",
        "measurement": f'<{ke_client.kb_id}/measurement/{random.randint(a: 1, b: 1000)}>',
    }, {...}]
    ]
    logging.info(f"Post offer:{sensor_measurements}")
    return sensor_measurements

# Initialize KI for the data demand.
# Handler will be called by the client after appropriate ASK KI appears in the system
@ke_client.answer("sensor-data")  tomasz_ciesielczyk *
def answer(ki_id, bindings):...
```

Figure 6. KI handlers for sample measurement client commands

II.4.2.e. Registration and running the client

```
# register client in the KE
ke_client.register()

ke_client.start() # start client in async mode
while True:
    # post offer every 15 seconds
    post_data()
    time.sleep(15)
```

Figure 7. KE client registration and running commands

III. STANDARDIZATION OF PROPRIETARY FLEXIBILITY FRAMEWORKS AND INTERFACES AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS (T5.2)

III.1. Description of the InterFlex framework

The InterFlex framework is a reference framework developed within the EU Horizon 2020 InterFlex project to support the interoperable exchange of flexibility information between flexibility providers, aggregators and grid or market actors. It defines a generic interaction model and standardized data structures for representing flexibility in an abstract and technology-agnostic way, typically using time-resolved power increase and decrease options with associated attributes such as duration and validity. The framework focuses on interoperability at the interface level and does not prescribe asset-level control, optimisation or market-clearing logic. Instead, it enables different systems and actors to communicate flexibility information in a consistent manner, allowing flexibility originating from heterogeneous infrastructures to be compared, evaluated and used by downstream services such as grid operation or market-oriented components (European Commission, 2020).

III.1.1. InterFlex framework for aggregators

The proprietary flexibility framework addressed in this section is designed to aggregate, manage, and expose flexibility originating exclusively from the operation of industrial waterworks. This use case corresponds to the Austrian demo pilot considered within the BlueBird project. The considered flexibility sources are limited to electrically driven water pumps and the associated water storage (retention) tank, which together enable temporal decoupling between electricity consumption and water demand.

The framework operates as an aggregator-level coordination layer between the waterworks automation system and external grid- and market-oriented services. It supports the prediction of water demand and power consumption, the scheduling of pump operation, and the optimized use of the water storage tank to shift electricity consumption in time while respecting operational and sanitary constraints.

To ensure interoperability with European flexibility solutions, the InterFlex framework for aggregators is adopted as a reference architecture. In this context, the InterFlex framework provides the conceptual interaction model used to structure and standardize the exchange of flexibility information between the waterworks-based system and external market or grid actors.

Within the proposed solution, proprietary interfaces and internal data representations related to pump operation and water storage are aligned with the InterFlex interaction model and mapped to the BlueBird data model. This enables a standardized, technology-agnostic description of flexibility availability, operational constraints and activation parameters derived from the waterworks processes.

The standardized approach supports the integration of the waterworks as a flexibility provider within a Virtual Power Plant context. It enables the utilization of three main use cases: prediction and scheduling of waterworks power consumption, optimized use of the water storage tank as a flexibility buffer, and the provision of aggregated flexibility to different flexibility markets. Furthermore, it enables a structured comparison with other standardized flexibility frameworks regarding integration effort and suitability for infrastructure-based flexibility assets.

Figure 8 Generalized conceptual architecture of flexibility aggregation

The figure illustrates a generalized conceptual architecture of flexibility aggregation. While the figure includes a broader range of assets such as buildings, EV charging, and DER, the same architectural principles apply to the waterworks-based use case considered in this section, which focuses on pump operation and water storage.

III.2. Software Output of T5.2 – Integration of a Technical Flexibility Service Provider with the APG Flexibility Platform

In the Austrian demo case, the flexibility aggregation is performed by a Technical Flexibility Service Provider (tFSP) operating a Virtual Power Plant (VPP). The VPP constitutes the technical infrastructure responsible for connecting distributed flexibility resources, aggregating their flexibility potentials, and coordinating their activation during the provision of system services. Typical flexibility resources considered in this context include batteries, electric vehicles, heat pumps, and other controllable loads connected within energy cells or energy communities.

In the configuration considered in the Austrian demo case, the tFSP is directly connected to the flexibility platform of the Austrian Transmission System Operator (APG). In this setup no additional commercial aggregator (cFSP) is involved. Consequently, the tFSP assumes the operational role of a Flexibility Service Provider (FSP) towards the TSO platform and interacts directly with the APG Crowd Balancing Platform (CBP) via standardized API interfaces.

The resource layer consists of the individual flexible resources and their operators, such as prosumers, energy community members, or asset operators. These resources provide controllable deviations from

their baseline operation and are connected to the tFSP-operated VPP through asset interfaces or optional pre-aggregation services. Each resource exposes its operational constraints, availability windows, and flexibility potential to the VPP.

The technical aggregation layer is implemented by the VPP operated by the tFSP. At this level, the flexibility potentials of multiple distributed assets are aggregated into flexibility pools and translated into a unified internal flexibility representation. Conceptually, this aggregation and interaction layer can build on the InterFlex framework, which provides a generic model for describing flexibility in terms of available power, activation direction, time constraints, and technical limitations. Within the VPP, this abstraction enables the aggregation of heterogeneous resources, the calculation of feasible flexibility pools, and the management of baseline operation and activation disaggregation. In this context, the InterFlex framework is used as a reference model for the internal representation and standardization of flexibility, while the actual external interaction with the TSO is implemented via the APG Crowd Balancing Platform interfaces.

The system operator interface layer connects the VPP to the APG flexibility platform. Communication with APG is realized via the REST-based interfaces of the Crowd Balancing Platform using the canonical data model defined for balancing services. Through this interface the tFSP participates directly in the balancing service processes defined by the TSO, including the registration of flexibility pools, submission of bids for balancing products, reception of activation signals, and provision of real-time measurement data.

Operationally, the interaction with the TSO follows the standard balancing service lifecycle. After successful prequalification and registration of the flexibility pools, the VPP submits bids for balancing capacity or balancing energy via the CBP interface. Following market clearing, the TSO transmits activation signals to the VPP. The VPP then disaggregates these activation commands to the individual flexible resources while continuously reporting measurements and operational status to the platform.

Within BlueBird, the Austrian demo case is used as a reference implementation of this integration architecture. By implementing and validating the direct integration between a tFSP-operated VPP and the APG flexibility platform, the project establishes a concrete technical template. The insights obtained from this implementation will subsequently be generalized to derive transferable architectural patterns and interoperability principles for flexibility integration in other European TSO and DSO environments.

III.2.1. System architecture of the APG integration

Conceptually, the architecture can be described in three functional layers.

III.2.1.a. Resource layer

The resource layer consists of the individual flexible resources and their operators, such as prosumers, energy community members, or asset operators. These resources provide controllable deviations from their baseline operation and are connected to the tFSP-operated VPP through asset interfaces or optional pre-aggregation services.

Each resource exposes its operational constraints, availability windows, and flexibility potential to the VPP.

III.2.1.b. Aggregation layer

The technical aggregation layer is implemented by the VPP operated by the tFSP. At this level, the flexibility potentials of multiple distributed assets are aggregated into flexibility pools and translated into a unified internal flexibility representation.

Conceptually, this aggregation and interaction layer can build on the InterFlex framework, which provides a generic model for describing flexibility in terms of available power, activation direction, time constraints, and technical limitations.

Within the VPP, this abstraction enables the aggregation of heterogeneous resources, the calculation of feasible flexibility pools, and the management of baseline operation and activation disaggregation.

III.2.1.c. System operator interface layer

The system operator interface layer connects the VPP to the APG flexibility platform. Communication with APG is realized via the REST-based interfaces of the Crowd Balancing Platform using the canonical data model defined for balancing services.

Through this interface the tFSP participates directly in the balancing service processes defined by the TSO, including:

- registration of flexibility pools
- submission of bids for balancing products
- reception of activation signals
- provision of real-time measurement data

In the Austrian operational and regulatory context, platform-based interaction via APG systems has become the relevant implementation pathway for participation in balancing service processes.

This framework enforces a harmonized interaction between flexibility providers and the transmission system operator, requiring all participating entities, including Technical Flexibility Service Providers, to communicate via the APG platform.

As a result, the direct integration of VPP-based flexibility aggregation systems with the APG interface is not only a technical design choice but necessary from an operational market-access perspective.

III.2.2. Operational workflow of the flexibility service

Operationally, the interaction with the TSO follows the standard balancing service lifecycle.

After successful prequalification and registration of the flexibility pools, the VPP submits bids for balancing capacity or balancing energy via the CBP interface. Following market clearing, the TSO transmits activation signals to the VPP.

The VPP then disaggregates these activation commands to the individual flexible resources while continuously reporting measurements and operational status to the platform.

Within BlueBird, the Austrian demo case is used as a reference implementation of this integration architecture. By implementing and validating the direct integration between a tFSP-operated VPP and the APG flexibility platform, the project establishes a concrete technical template.

III.2.3. Comparative analysis of flexibility frameworks

To evaluate the suitability of different interoperability frameworks for flexibility integration, a comparative analysis was performed considering the following criteria:

- interoperability
- implementation complexity
- compatibility with market platforms
- scalability for distributed resources

The most relevant frameworks considered in this analysis include the InterFlex framework, standardized IEC-based approaches, and proprietary flexibility platforms.

Table 2. Comparative analysis of flexibility frameworks

Framework	Main focus	Advantages	Limitations
InterFlex	flexibility interoperability	technology-agnostic, modular	requires mapping to market models
IEC CIM	grid data model	standardized utility model	complex implementation
Proprietary VPP models	asset optimisation	efficient control	limited interoperability

Based on this analysis, the InterFlex framework was selected as the most suitable reference model for representing flexibility in the BlueBird pilot, as it provides a flexible abstraction layer while maintaining compatibility with different market interfaces. This alignment enables the standardized representation and exchange of flexibility information while maintaining compatibility with market-oriented interfaces such as the APG Crowd Balancing Platform.

III.3. Pseudocode of the APG interface implementation

To support the implementation of the described integration architecture, a reference pseudocode implementation of the APG interface has been developed within Task T5.2. The following simplified pseudocode examples illustrate key interface mechanisms used for communication between the Virtual Power Plant and the APG Crowd Balancing Platform.

```
function get_access_token():
    if token_cache.access_token valid (now < expires_at - TOKEN_REFRESH_SAFETY):
        return token_cache.access_token

    response = HTTP.POST(OAUTH_TOKEN_URL, auth=(CLIENT_ID, CLIENT_SECRET),
                        body="grant_type=client_credentials")
    token_cache.access_token = response.access_token
    token_cache.expires_at = now + response.expires_in
    return token_cache.access_token
```

Figure 9. Example pseudocode: OAuth authentication

```
function handle_SAM(payload):
    sam = parse_SAM(payload)
    dispatch_setpoint_to_assets(sam.quantity)
```

Figure 10. Example pseudocode: Activation handling

The pseudocode describes the logical structure of the interface components responsible for authentication, bid submission, activation handling, and telemetry reporting between the Virtual Power Plant and the APG Crowd Balancing Platform.

The complete pseudocode is available in the public GitHub repository [6] BlueBird Flexibility Trading module (T5.3).

IV. TRADING MANAGER DESCRIPTION (T5.3)

The Trading Manager (TM) is a core component of the BlueBird project, responsible for enabling interaction with multiple energy markets and providing market-related intelligence to other system components, in particular the Flexibility Manager (FM). Its primary function is to acquire energy price data—covering both energy production and energy consumption—for defined time intervals and to deliver this information in a structured form suitable for further optimisation and decision-making processes. Sources are hosted at GitHub public repository [<https://github.com/BlueBird-project/trading-manager>, 7]. The TM is designed to support pilots operating in heterogeneous market environments. When price information is available from multiple energy markets for the same time horizon, the TM performs comparative analysis and estimates the most advantageous prices from the perspective of the requesting pilot. This analysis takes into account market characteristics, temporal granularity, and the specific requirements of the pilot, ensuring that the delivered results are aligned with operational and economic objectives.

In more advanced scenarios, the TM is capable of processing information related to potential energy production and consumption, which may be provided in the form of mathematical functions or other abstract representations. Based on these inputs and optionally including additional cost functions (e.g. operational constraints, penalties, or external costs), the TM computes the optimal production and consumption strategy that minimises costs or maximises economic benefits over time. This functionality supports strategic planning and operational optimisation across different market conditions.

Due to the fundamental differences between energy market mechanisms, the TM provides two complementary operational modes:

- **Capacity Market mode** - in this mode, the TM uses consumption, production, and additional cost functions as inputs to determine the optimal production and consumption levels for each discrete time unit. The result is a time-resolved schedule that represents the most economically efficient strategy under capacity market constraints.
- **Other energy market modes** (e.g. day-ahead, intraday, balancing markets) - for these markets, the TM focuses on delivering the best available energy prices for a specified time window. The TM analyses relevant market data and returns the most favourable prices for both energy production and consumption, without enforcing a full optimisation of production or consumption profiles.

From a technical standpoint, the TM retrieves market data by issuing structured queries via the Knowledge Engine, which serves as the interoperability and data exchange layer within the BlueBird architecture. The Knowledge Engine enables uniform access to heterogeneous data sources, abstracts differences between market interfaces, and ensures consistent data representation.

In addition to historical and current market data, the TM can also obtain forecasted energy prices by interacting with a dedicated forecasting service developed as part of the BlueBird project. This allows the TM to support forward-looking analyses and planning activities, which are essential for predictive optimisation and proactive decision-making in dynamic energy systems.

To realise the above functionality, this deliverable describes two concrete implementation solutions developed within the BlueBird project:

- a client component responsible for communicating with external energy market services through the Knowledge Engine, handling data retrieval, normalisation, and validation;
- a client component for interfacing with the BlueBird forecasting service, enabling access to predicted energy prices and supporting scenario-based analysis.

Together, these components establish the Trading Manager as a flexible, extensible, and interoperable module capable of supporting a wide range of pilot use cases and market configurations within the BlueBird project.

IV.1. Market connectors

Sources of the custom market plugins for TM are available at <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/tm-market-plugins>.

IV.1.1. Client for ENTSO-E Transparency market platform

The ENTSO-E Transparency Platform webpage is an online portal that provides free, centralised access to pan-European electricity market data. It was created by the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) [<https://transparency.entsoe.eu/market>, 9].

Figure 11 ENTSO-E Transparency Platform webpage!

IV.1.1.a. REST API

WP5 will provide a Python service providing data from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform over the KE network. Each service instance will require an access token – which can be requested after registering at the ENTSO-E platform. Client service code will be published in the GitHub repository and the service will be dockerized.

Sample HTTP request:

```
https://web-api.tp.entsoe.eu/api?securityToken={token}&documentType=A44&periodStart=202512170000&periodEnd=202512190000&out_Domain=10Y1001A1001A82H&in_Domain=10Y1001A1001A82&contract_MarketAgreement.type=A01&classificationSequence_AttributeInstanceComponent.position=1
```

Figure 12. Sample HTTP request to retrieve data from the Germany day ahead market

Response:

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<Publication_MarketDocument xmlns="urn:iec62325.351:tc57wg16:451-3:publicationdocument:7:3">
  <mRID>5b11db0d1b224c69853e266bf34ee544</mRID>
  <revisionNumber>1</revisionNumber>
  <type>A44</type>
  <sender_MarketParticipant.mRID codingScheme="A01">10X1001A1001A450</sender_MarketParticipant.mRID>
  <sender_MarketParticipant.marketRole.type>A32</sender_MarketParticipant.marketRole.type>
  <receiver_MarketParticipant.mRID codingScheme="A01">10X1001A1001A450</receiver_MarketParticipant.mRID>
  <receiver_MarketParticipant.marketRole.type>A33</receiver_MarketParticipant.marketRole.type>
  <createdDateTime>2025-12-18T12:01:56Z</createdDateTime>
  <period.timeInterval>
    <start>2025-12-16T23:00Z</start>
    <end>2025-12-18T23:00Z</end>
  </period.timeInterval>
  <TimeSeries>
    <mRID>1</mRID>
    <auction.type>A01</auction.type>
    <businessType>A62</businessType>
    <in_Domain.mRID codingScheme="A01">10Y1001A1001A82H</in_Domain.mRID>
    <out_Domain.mRID codingScheme="A01">10Y1001A1001A82H</out_Domain.mRID>
    <contract_MarketAgreement.type>A01</contract_MarketAgreement.type>
    <currency_Unit.name>EUR</currency_Unit.name>
    <price_Measure_Unit.name>MWh</price_Measure_Unit.name>
    <classificationSequence_AttributeInstanceComponent.position>1</classificationSequence_AttributeInstanceComponent.position>
    <curveType>A03</curveType>
    <Period>
      <timeInterval>
        <start>2025-12-16T23:00Z</start>
        <end>2025-12-17T23:00Z</end>
      </timeInterval>
    </Period>
  </TimeSeries>
</Publication_MarketDocument>

```

Figure 13. Sample HTTP response to retrieve data from the Germany day ahead market

IV.1.2. Client for accessing BlueBird price forecasting service

The TM will communicate with the BlueBird price forecasting Digital Twin through the KE – leveraging appropriate graph patterns – similarly like market clients. The forecasting service will act as a market client from the TM perspective.

V. CONCLUSION

V.1. Summary of WP5 preliminary technical outputs

This document presents an overview of the software to be delivered within Work Package 5 (WP5) of the BlueBird project. The software has been designed and developed in accordance with the assumptions and requirements provided by the project partners and is primarily intended to support the delivery of energy price information from various energy markets to the Flexibility Manager (FM).

The information provided by the WP5 software enables the FM to make informed decisions related to energy production, consumption, and flexibility optimisation, taking into account market conditions and economic factors across different energy markets.

The purpose of this document is to facilitate the effective use of the developed software by providing clear descriptions of its functionality, configuration options, and integration points. It also presents illustrative examples of typical usage scenarios and application cases, helping users and integrators to better understand how the software components can be deployed and utilised within the BlueBird system architecture. Additionally, the document aims to clarify key configuration aspects and operational considerations, thereby supporting smooth installation, integration, and further development of the WP5 software components.

V.2. Next steps toward D5.2

Within the BlueBird project, two deliverables are foreseen for Work Package 5 (WP5). The first deliverable is described in the present document, while the second one is scheduled to be delivered in month 30 of the project. The latter will provide a comprehensive description of the final version of the software developed within WP5.

The final deliverable will represent a natural evolution and maturation of the services introduced and described in this document. The functionality of these services will be significantly extended, refined, and thoroughly tested to ensure robustness, scalability, and compliance with project objectives.

Importantly, the development of the final software version will not be limited to the initial requirements provided by project partners at the beginning of the project. Instead, it will incorporate updated and refined requirements gathered throughout the project lifecycle, including feedback from pilot implementations, technical evaluations, and evolving use-case scenarios. This iterative and adaptive approach will ensure that the final WP5 software solutions effectively address real-world needs and deliver maximum value to the BlueBird pilots and stakeholders.

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